

A DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITE ARTIFICIAL LEG SHELL USING RTM PROCESS

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SUMMARY: Composite artificial leg shell was designed and its manufacturing process by Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) was studied. Reinforcement and resin were characterized for the optimization of the process. In order to achieve high fiber volume contents of the part, the optimal process conditions were found based on the characterization of resin viscosity. And flow analyses were performed using the model developed for irregular cross-section cylindrical shell structure. Under the selected conditions (the mold temperature and the resin feed rate), the leg shell was manufactured. The fabricated part would be tested if it satisfies required static and dynamic load conditions.

KEYWORDS: artificial leg shell, RTM process, process optimization, optimization by viscosity characterization, flow analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The resin flow plays a crucial role in the manufacturing of leg shell using resin transfer molding (RTM) process. The parameters affecting the resin flow are resin viscosity, reinforcement permeability and pressure gradient induced by the process conditions. The flow through reinforcements fabrics, therefore, can be described by the well known Darcy's law [1]

$$\bar{U}_D = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (1)$$

where \bar{U}_D is the average or Darcian velocity of the resin, μ is the resin viscosity, ∇P is the pressure gradient induced in porous media and K is the permeability of reinforcements.

Permeability is only dependent on the type and the geometry of reinforcements. Widely used form for permeability is Carman-Kozeny equation [1,2]

$$K = \frac{R_f^2 (1 - v_f)^3}{4k_{ii} v_f^2} \quad (2)$$

Where R_f is radius of single fiber, v_f is fiber volume fraction and k_{ii} is Kozeny constant and it varies when the angle between resin flow direction and fiber alignments changes.

In normal RTM process, the usual fiber volume content of the part is between 10-20%. Such that the resin flow velocity is large enough to fill the mold perfectly before the gelation of resin. But if the fiber volume fraction of the part is increased, the flow resistance is increased

rapidly and the permeability is also decreased surprisingly(Fig.1). Mold filling conditions, therefore, in advanced RTM process has to be taken into account carefully. And there needs the optimization of process temperature and pressure.

Fig.1 Permeability Ratio Based on the Permeability of $v_f=0.2$

Resin viscosity also effects largely on rein flow. Viscosity is usually a function of a temperature and an elapsed time after mixing of resin components to its gelation. If a mold is heated up, reaction of thermosetting polymer is accelerated due to the temperature effect. The optimal mold temperature should be found to maximize the resin flow.

CHARACTERIZATION OF REINFORCEMENTS

Knitted Carbon fabric(Unidirectional 6K bundle, Toray T300) is used for the reinforcements of the shell. The Pattern of the preform is given Fig.2 (here, fiber is Kevlar 49 for good observation of pattern). Cylindrical Preform is fabricated where the radius of cylinder changes. Permeability of fabrics is determined using the resin fronts measured from the experiment(Fig.3). In the experiment, constant inlet pressure is applied. Silicone oil is used . And the resin fronts as a function of time are measured. With the equation (2) and resin fronts, Permeability of preform are calculated [3,4].

Fig.2 Pattern of the Knitted Preform used in the Process

Fig.3 Experimental Setup for the Measurement of Preform Permeability

Fiber radius(R_f) is a value given by the manufacturer. Using the permeability measured in the experiments, the Kozeny constant is fitted(Fig.4). And the result is used to determine the permeability of preform when flow analysis is performed.

$$R_f = 4.0 \quad \mu\text{m} \quad (3)$$

$$k_{ii} = 0.43(4)$$

Fig.4 Experimentally Measured Permeability of the Preform

CHARACTERIZATION OF MATRIX

In RTM process for high fiber volume contents, the resin viscosity has a big effect on the mold filling time. And low viscosity CIBA-GEIGY LY564 epoxy resin is used for the matrix system and the hardener is HY2954. Recommended mixing ratio of LY564 and HY2954 by weight is 100 and 35, respectively. Resin viscosity is measured and cure of resin is analyzed.

Resin Viscosity

Viscosity(Fig.5) is measured using Brookfield cone and plate type viscometer(CAP2000). Viscosity changes as mixed resin reacts chemically with time but the change is not large in low temperature range. But total mold fill time of less than 30 minutes is preferred for the good properties of the part. Measured viscosity is used to determine optimal process.

Fig.5 Measured Viscosity of Epoxy Resin(CIBA-GEIGY:LY564+HY2954)

Cure of the Resin

Cure kinetics modeling of LY564 epoxy resin can be performed by the quantification of heat released from the reaction. Released heats were measured using differential scanning calorimeter(DSC). The procedure of modeling is given in detail by reference 5. The reactive equations and the constants determined are given as follows.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{H_T}{H_U} \frac{d\beta}{dt} \quad (5)$$

where α is degree of cure, β is isothermal degree of cure, $d\alpha/dt$ is rate of cure, $d\beta/dt$ is isothermal rate of cure, H_T is isothermal heat of reaction and H_U is ultimate heat of reaction.

$$\frac{H_T}{H_U} = a + b \cdot T \quad (6)$$

$$a = -0.5984 \quad b = 4.241 \times 10^{-3} \quad (7)$$

where H_T/H_U is ratio of heat of reaction, T is absolute temperature.

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\beta^m)(1-\beta)^n \quad (8)$$

$$K_1 = A_1 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E_1}{RT}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$K_2 = A_2 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E_2}{RT}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$A_1 = -1.10 \times 10^2 \quad \Delta E_1 = -4.60 \times 10^3 \quad (11)$$

$$A_2 = 8.60 \times 10^3 \quad \Delta E_2 = -5.18 \times 10^3 \quad (12)$$

$$m = 0.25 \quad n = 1.425 \quad (13)$$

Here K_1 and K_2 are the coefficients dependent on the temperature, m and n are the constants independent on the temperature and R is the universal gas constant.

Fig.6 Comparison of Degree of Cure between measurements and predictions by the Model

To verify the model, the measured degree of cure and calculated values are compared (Fig.6). As can be seen from the comparison(Fig. 6), the measurements and the predictions show good agreements. Now if a specific cure cycle is given, the degree of cure can be calculated by integrating equation 6 with time.

Fig.7 Cure Cycle of Epoxy Resin(CIBA-GEIGY:LY564+HY2954)

Adequate cure of the resin is needed for good mechanical property of composites parts. Two step cure is recommended by the manufacturer. Pre-cure is for low shrinkage and post-cure is for uniform cure and low internal stresses. Determined cure cycle is given in Fig.7. Here the gelation temperature is 80 and it should not be higher than absolutely necessary to maintain low shrinkage as well as low internal stresses. Second step temperature 120 is applied for post cure.

PROCESS OPTIMIZATION AND FABRICATION

A simple model to predict resin flow for any kind of irregular cross-section cylindrical shell structure is developed through the characterization of resin viscosity measured. To find optimal process conditions, parameter study was performed as a mold temperature changes. Under the determined optimal conditions, composite artificial leg shell was manufactured and processability is verified.

Optimal Process Conditions

A simple flow analysis model which can be applicable to the shape of irregular cross-section cylindrical shell structure is derived. Definitions used are given in Fig.8. $A(x)$ changes gradually. The model here is derived based on the constant flow rate.

Fig.8 Calculation Domain Used for Flow Analysis

From the resin mass conservation, relation between Darcian velocity and flow area is

$$Q_I = \bar{U}_{D,I} A_I = \bar{U}_{D,x} A_x = \text{constant} \quad (14)$$

where Q_I is flow rate in inlet, $\bar{U}_{D,I}$ is Darcian velocity in inlet, A_I is flow cross-section area in inlet, $\bar{U}_{D,x}$ is Darcian velocity at specified x position, A_x is flow area at that position.

Also, from the resin mass conservation, a relation between resin front and time is

$$Q_I \cdot t_f = (1 - v_f) \int_0^{x_f} A(x) dx \quad (15)$$

where t_f is the time when the resin front reaches x_f .

Using equation 15, resin fronts as the time goes, (t_f, x_f) , can be calculated.

By integrating Darcy's law along the total flow field, inlet pressure is obtained as follows

$$\int_0^{x_f} \bar{U}_{D,x} \cdot \mu(t_x) dx = K \int_0^{P_I} dp = KP_I \quad (16)$$

The above equation is rearranged using equation 14

$$P_I = \frac{1}{K} \int_0^{x_f} \bar{U}_{D,x} \cdot \mu(t_x) dx = \frac{Q_I}{K} \int_0^{x_f} \frac{\mu(t_x)}{A(x)} dx \quad (17)$$

Optimal process condition can be obtained by minimizing inlet pressure in case of constant flow rate. In high fiber contents RTM process, to fill a mold fully high inlet pressure is necessary. And high inlet pressure can cause wrinkles of preform in early stage of filling. Gradual increase of inlet pressure, nearly the same as constant flow rate, is adequate.

As can be seen from equation 17, $\int_0^{x_f} \mu(t_x)/A(x) dx$ should be minimized to minimize inlet pressure. $A(x)$ is automatically determined if the geometry of the part is given. Therefore, minimization of $\int_0^{x_f} \mu(t_x)/A(x) dx$ is the same as minimization of $\int_0^{x_f} \mu(t_x) dx$. As $A(x)$ changes gradually, x are nearly linearly dependent on t_x . So minimization of $\int_0^{x_f} \mu(t_x) dx$ is the same as minimization of $\int_0^{t_f} \mu(t_x) dt_x$

$$\text{Minimization of Inlet Pressure} \Rightarrow \text{Minimization of } \int_0^{t_f} \mu(t_x) dt_x \quad (18)$$

Above equation means that process optimization can be easily done by the measured viscosity. The above result is more definite if the equation is derived for constant flow area.

$$P_I = \frac{Q_I}{KA_I} \int_0^{x_f} \mu(t_x) dx = \frac{Q_I^2}{\epsilon KA_I^2} \int_0^{t_f} \mu(t_x) dt_x \quad \Leftarrow \quad x = \frac{Q_I}{\epsilon A_I} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 9 Integral of Measured Viscosities with Times

The integral of $\int_0^{t_f} \mu(t_x) dt_x$ is given in Fig.9. As can be seen from the figure, there exists optimal process temperature. Ratio of Viscosity Integrations Based on the Value of Temperature 50 °C is given in Fig.10. Viscosity effect due to temperature is well shown.

Fig.10 Ratio of Viscosity Integrations Based on the Value of Temperature 50 °C

To find adequate process conditions, parameter studies of mold filling process(Fig.11) were performed using the developed model. Fiber volume content of preform under the inner pressure and flow area of each region are

$$v_f = 0.45 \quad (20)$$

$$A(x) = 3.7699 \quad [\text{cm}^2] \quad 0 \leq x \leq 5.3, \quad \text{region I} \quad (21)$$

$$= 3.7699 + 0.364(x - 5.3) \quad [\text{cm}^2] \quad 5.3 \leq x \leq 10.9, \quad \text{region II} \quad (22)$$

$$= 5.8083 + 0.182(x - 10.9) \quad [\text{cm}^2] \quad 10.9 \leq x \leq 18.5, \quad \text{region III} \quad (23)$$

$$= 7.1915 + 0.091(x - 18.5) \quad [\text{cm}^2] \quad 18.5 \leq x \leq 26.7, \quad \text{region IV} \quad (24)$$

$$= 7.9377 - 0.6(5 - \sqrt{25 - (x - 26.7)^2}) \quad [\text{cm}^2] \quad 26.7 \leq x \leq 30.0, \quad \text{region V} \quad (25)$$

Inlet pressures are calculated as a function of temperature under the constant flow rate ($Q_I = 0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{sec}$, $Q_I = 0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{sec}$). In case of flow rate $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{sec}$, mold fill time is a little longer and inlet pressure is dominated by the effect of resin cure. If the mold temperature is high enough (60, 70 °C), the resin is not filled perfectly. But if the mold temperature is low enough (20 °C), extremely high pressure is needed for perfect filling. There needs increase of flow rate.

(a) Flow Rate = 0.05 cm³/sec

Flow Rate = 0.1 cm³/sec

Fig.11 Inlet Pressure Calculated for Two Constant Flow Rate Cases

In case of flow rate 0.1 cm³/sec, adequate pressure is obtained for the mold temperature 50 ° C. Even though the mold temperature 60 ° C shows lower pressure, rapid increase of pressure is found in end region. It is due to resin cure. It is not good for optimal process because we needs time gap for oven cure, and so on. Determined optimal condition is as follows

$$Temperature_{MOLD} = 50 \quad [^{\circ}C] \quad (26)$$

Manufacturing of the Shell

For an easier application of RTM process, the shape of shell is changed a little(Fig.12). In other words, every holes and slit are filled with preform.

Fig.12 Shape of shell and Geometry for Flow Analysis

Mold filling process is schematically explained in Fig.13. Constant flow rate is achieved by constant movement of piston in a cylinder of resin reservoir. Piston speed is controlled by DC servo motor connected with computer. Inlet pressure is measured by pressure transducer. Polyurethane film is used inside the shell to compress the preform.

Fig.13 Schematic of Mold Filling Process

The shape of shell is supported by the pressure applied inside the shell. The pressure is supplied by nitrogen gas and it is kept on constant during the process. It is high enough compared with resin inlet pressure. After mold filling, the mold is put inside oven and the resin is cured according to the cure cycle determined(Fig.7).

$$P_{inside\ the\ shell} = 15 \quad [atm] \quad (27)$$

Steel mold is adapted to the process(Fig.14). It is composed of four pieces. Added parts for the easiness of manufacturing are cut away after the cure. And final product of the shell is given in Fig. 15.

Fig.14 Picture of the Mold Used in the Process

Fig.15 Final Form of Manufactured Artificial Leg Shell

CONCLUSION

Flow analysis model based on the characterization of resin viscosity is suggested. The model can be easily applied to any kind of irregular cross-section cylindrical shell structure. To find optimal process conditions, parameter study was performed based on the model developed. Under the selected optimal conditions, composite artificial leg shell was manufactured. Now, the parts should be evaluated whether it satisfies required load conditions. And to obtain desired mechanical properties, void content of the part has to be checked.

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